

**Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital heAlth Technology dEsiGn In
sub saharan afriCa (STRATEGIC)**

Deliverable No. 6.2

Exploitation and Advocacy Action Plan

Submission date

30 September 2024

**This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon Europe programme Global Health EDCTP3 Joint
Undertaking Under Grant Agreement no. 101145644**

Document Control

Deliverable	D6.2: Exploitation and Advocacy Action Plan
WP/Task Related	WP6/Task 6.1 (Communication strategy and actions) and Task 6.2 (Dissemination and exploitation strategy and actions)
Delivery Date	30 September 2024 submitted version
Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Partner	University Eduardo Mondlane (UEM)
Contributors	All Consortium Partners: University of Nottingham (UoN), Ghana Health Services (GHS), European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC), University of Yaoundé I (LETS) and Libera Università degli Studi Maria Ss Assunta di Roma (LUMSA)
Reviewers	University of Nottingham (UoN)
Abstract	This document describes Exploitation & Advocacy Actions that are planned which complements the Communication & Dissemination Actions (deliverable 6.1). The document aims to concisely present the tangible and intangible exploitable outputs and actions to be implemented during the project duration as well as after the project ends. Because the exploitation and advocacy actions are dependent on project's outputs, this document is expected to be dynamic and thus will be updated and adapted depending on the progress and evolution of the project.
Key Words	Exploitation, advocacy, Stakeholders

Revision History

Version	Date	Lead Author(s)	Reviewer(s)	Notes
0.1	24.09.2024	Sidat MM	University of Nottingham (UoN)	First Draft
0.2	29.09.2024	Sidat MM	University of Nottingham (UoN)	Second Draft

TABLE OF CONTENT

Document Control.....	2
Revision History	2
Executive Summary:.....	3
List of acronyms/abbreviations	4
1. Brief Introduction to STRATEGIC Project	5
2. Overall Goals	5
2.1 Exploitation Strategy.....	6
Table 1: Summary of path, strategic goals and measures for exploitation activities of the STRATEGIC project	7
Table 2: Summary of target groups, exploitable outcomes and desired impact	8
2.2 Advocacy Strategy	9
2.2. Community and Ecosystem Building.....	10
2.3. Contributions of Different WPs and Coordination	10

Executive Summary:

STRATEGIC’s exploitation and advocacy plan outlines the strategic approach to ensure the long-term sustainability, adoption, and impact of the co-created frameworks, training materials for ethical reviews and regulations of digital technologies in clinical trials and research. The

plan focuses on leveraging the project’s outputs to influence key stakeholders, ensure widespread use of the project outputs and integrating the results into regulatory and clinical practices across Africa and the European Union and globally. Basically, the plan outlines the strategies and activities which aim to ensure impact and secure a legacy for the project. Furthermore, the plan also outlines how stakeholders and target groups (National Ethics Committees, National Regulatory Agencies and, others) will be engaged to ensure the transfer of knowledge and project outputs and enable its exploitation and adoption in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Additionally, it aims to contribute to effective actions which appropriately address the ethical and legal challenges of digital health technologies in SSA. This document represents the deliverable 6.2 (Exploitation & Advocacy Plan) and it complements the deliverable 6.1 (Communication and Dissemination Plan).

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description/Explanation
EAP	Exploitation & Advocacy Plan
EU	European Union
EDCTP	European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key performance indicators
NECs	National Ethics Committees
NRA	National Regulatory Agencies
SSA	sub-Saharan Africa

1. Brief Introduction to STRATEGIC Project

The STRATEGIC Project's vision is to co-create a culturally sensitive responsible research and innovation approach and to strengthen existing ethics and regulatory capacities for socially acceptable design and deployment of digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Thus, the STRATEGIC project seeks to generate impact by contributing to ensure a responsible integration of digital health technologies into clinical research and practice and based on adequate international standards in SSA.

Three partners from Africa and four from Europe are part of the STRATEGIC consortium and they bring together international expertise on ethics reviews, research ethics, technology ethics and law and clinical research and practice. The consortium is made of partners from English, French and Portuguese speaking countries of SSA and from EU which collectively offer diverse experiences and expertise with significant networks relevant for achieving all objectives defined for the STRATEGIC project.

This document is organised in a way that intends to guide the project partners on strategies, activities and actions related to exploitation and advocacy to achieve the defined goals of the STRATEGIC project. However, it is important to mention that the exploitation and advocacy activities and actions will be based on work packages (WP1: Scientific Coordination and Outreach), mapping and engagement of stakeholders in SSA (WP2 and WP3), development of responsible innovation approaches and its integration into Ethics review processes in SSA activities and actions in SSA (WP4) and development (co-creation) and implementation of a training for the National Ethics Committees (NECs) and National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) and Higher Education Institutions in SSA (WP5).

2. Overall Goals

This plan outlines how STRATEGIC will achieve goals of exploitation, advocacy and sustainability. This task is fundamentally dependent on the stakeholder identification mapping being done in WP3. For STRATEGIC, the definition of these concepts is critical.

Exploitation: Ensure the uptake and application of the project outcomes by key stakeholders (ethics committees, regulatory bodies, clinical researchers, and technology developers).

Advocacy: Promote the framework to policymakers, ethics review boards, and the broader research community to embed ethical standards in digital technology use for clinical trials.

Sustainability: Create long-term pathways for the project output's integration into existing

guidelines and ethics review processes.

2.1 Exploitation Strategy

The STRATEGIC's exploitation strategy focuses on making relevant project results widely accessible and usable by the relevant stakeholders, including regulators, clinical trial researchers, ethics committees, digital technology developers, and academic institutions.

2.1.1 Key Exploitable Outputs

- **Responsible digital health technology framework:** A comprehensive, practical framework co-created to review the ethical use of digital technologies in clinical trials and research.
- **STRATEGIC's capacity development plan and resources:** A range of resources that include training modules and materials for several stakeholders include NECs and RECs.
- **Use case reports:** Detailed reports from live use cases to serve as good practice examples and pitfalls to avoid.

2.1.2 Exploitation Pathways

- **Direct Adoption by NECS and RECs:** Promoting the framework for direct use by ethics review boards through capacity-building workshops and webinars. To achieve this, NECs and RECs in Africa have been identified as critical stakeholders and will be involved in the project from the beginning.
- **Integration into Regulatory Guidelines:** STRATEGIC is working relevant RECs hopes to connect with national and European regulatory bodies (e.g., EMA, national health authorities) through our partner EUREC to achieve integration of the framework into existing clinical trial regulations and guidelines for digital health technologies.
- **Academic and Training Programs:** STRATEGIC will work to see if developed framework and training materials can be incorporated into academic curricula for bioethics, clinical trial design, and digital health technology courses, ensuring that future professionals are well-versed in ethical considerations for digital tools.

2.1.3 Target Stakeholders

- **Ethics Committees:** Direct users of the framework, who will review digital

technologies in clinical trials and research projects.

- **Regulatory Bodies:** National and international regulatory agencies that oversee clinical trials.
- **Healthcare and Pharma Industries:** Clinical trial sponsors and technology providers who need to comply with ethical standards.
- **Academic and Research Institutions:** Universities and research centers involved in clinical trials and digital health research.
- **Digital Health Technology Developers:** Companies developing digital tools for clinical use (e.g., AI algorithms, wearables, mobile health apps).

2.2.4 Model for Sustainability

Collaboration with Professional Bodies: STRATEGIC is working with partner with a professional association the European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC) as a partner to embed the framework into their practices and guidelines. EUREC is a leading entity in ethics reviews in Europe and their expertise will guide STRATEGIC to achieve our exploitation goals.

Four complementary distinct exploitation paths will support the core exploitation strategy which promotes the holistic platform developed in the project, as outlined in table 1.

Table 1: Summary of path, strategic goals and measures for exploitation activities of the STRATEGIC project

Path	Strategic Goals
Joint exploitation of responsible digital health technology framework	Establishing a viable route to adoption for STRATEGIC’s framework.
Joint exploitation of STRATEGIC’s capacity development plan and resources	Promoting the adoption of the capacity development plan, training, centres and materials.
Joint exploitation of Virtual Open Educational Resources Hub (VOER)	Wider adoption of the Virtual Open Educational Resources Hub among partners and interested parties.
Use cases (UCs) for Exploitation	Expanding and exploiting the use cases; Use of STRATEGIC’s outcomes by other digital health innovators

In Table 2, summary of target groups, exploitable outcomes and expected impact is presented.

Table 2: Summary of target groups, exploitable outcomes and desired impact

Target groups	Exploitable outcomes	Desired Impact
TG1: Policy makers, Legal authorities (e.g., NRAs) TG2: Ethical authorities (e.g., NECs) TG3: Other public authorities TG4: Researchers, Digital Health Innovators, Higher Education/Training Institutions TG5: Citizens, Ethicists & Civil Society	EO1: Extensive research analysis and assessment ethics review infrastructure on addressing ethics of digital health technologies EO2: Human-centered and ethical assessment framework for approval of digital technologies in clinical research and practice EO3: Principles and regulations to underpin the design and deployment of digital health technologies EO4: Framework for trusted, safe and transparent digital health technology design EO5: Developed and implemented capacity development plans and resources on how to address ethics of digital health technology EO6: Training materials for the stakeholders and skills endowment; increasing awareness and literacy in ethics of digital health technologies EO7: Increase in trust of	Ethical and Legal Impact: - Inclusion and equity in the design and deployment of digital health technologies for clinical research and practice - Compliance with data protection and privacy principles - Ensuring responsible use of digital health technologies - Ensuring that ethical standards based on human rights are set and met by research and innovation in clinical settings - Improving the efficiency of the ethics and legal infrastructure for digital health technologies - Increasing the knowledge and skills base for improved ethics and regulatory capacity Societal Impact: - Improved, transparent, fair, safe, and trusted digital innovation and policies - Increase citizens' awareness and create societal change - Improve citizens' engagement and involvement in policy making

	<p>citizens in the design and deployment of digital health technologies</p> <p>EO8: Organizational and digital health innovations governance blueprints</p>	<p>- Enhance ethical and digital transformation in clinical research and practice</p> <p>Technology/Scientific Impact:</p> <p>- Enhanced scientific research/novel findings via agile and trustworthy digital innovations</p>
--	---	---

2.2 Advocacy Strategy

The advocacy strategy aims to build awareness, create demand, and ensure that STRATEGIC’s outputs influence policy, regulation, and practice. Advocacy will involve key stakeholders at various levels, from local to National decision-makers in Africa and Europe.

2.2.1 Key Message for Stakeholders

- **The Need for Ethics Review of Digital Technologies:** Digital technologies in clinical trials pose unique ethical challenges, and current review processes are not equipped to handle the rapid development and deployment of such tools.
- **The Benefits of co-created framework and training materials:** The framework and the training materials to be developed by STRATEGIC will address these gaps by providing clear guidelines to ensure the responsible and ethical use of digital technologies, enhancing trust, and protecting trial participants.
- **Aligning with Policy Goals:** The STRATEGIC outputs support African and European policy goals around responsible innovation, data protection, and ensuring fairness and transparency in healthcare research.

2.2.2 Advocacy Channels

- **Policy Advocacy:**
 - Engaging with African and European national health policymakers to raise awareness of the STRATEGIC output’s value in shaping future clinical trial regulations. To achieve this, a policy roundtable is already planned in WP4
 - Submit white papers and policy briefs to AU and EU bodies such as the African

Union; European Commission, and EMA (European Medicines Agency). Policy briefs will be developed as D4.2 within WP4

- **Public Engagement:**
 - Launch public awareness campaigns to inform the general public about the ethical challenges of digital technologies in clinical trials
 - Use social media, public webinars, and digital platforms to reach out to broader communities, including patient advocacy groups and civil society organisations.
- **Scientific and Professional Networks:**
 - Publish the framework and its supporting materials in peer-reviewed journals.
 - Present findings at major conferences, such as the World Conference on Research Integrity or the annual meetings of research ethics and clinical trial associations.
 - Using our partnership with EUREC to connect with wider networks working on related topics.

2.2. Community and Ecosystem Building

The STRATEGIC project will create an e-Community based on stakeholders mapping and engagement activities (WP 2 and WP3). The dynamics of this community will be defined and implemented by Task6.3. This e-community will be made of policymakers, digital health technology industry members and researchers and teachers from academia and will try to increase the pool of young research ethics experts and facilitate exchange and mentoring, as well as developing a technology research ethics trainer community to stimulate discourse on technology research ethics and facilitate good practice. Within these tasks, we also aim to develop and implement a targeted advocacy strategy to promote STRATEGIC solutions and co-creation of training modules. This will involve engaging with African Union, regional and national policy makers as well as stakeholders in academia and industry. The community-building efforts here will build on and extend the work started by EU projects ENERI and currently expanded by iRECs. Virtual Open Educational Resources Hub (VOER) will also be exploited to disseminate STRATEGIC's outcomes. The e-community will lead to the formation of a new legal entity that will become a legacy partner taking forward the Hub.

2.3. Contributions of Different WPs and Coordination

These exploitation and advocacy strategies are based on the results from WPs 2, 2, 4 and 5. WP6 leader will coordinate efforts across all WPs and with WP leaders via regular WP6 meetings. Additionally, an online form will be developed by WP6 to collect KPIs, exploitation and advocacy activities. The coordination challenge that STRATEGIC anticipates is related to adequately building research ethics and regulatory capacity in sub-Saharan Africa. This presupposes not only the identification and development of an appropriate approach and defined framework, but also sustainable cooperation with main actors (e.g., NECs and NRAs) and key stakeholders (e.g., healthcare workers, patients, industry, civil society groups) and to ensure that the approaches are actually implemented and further refined in line with ongoing technological progress. The STRATEGIC project partners also bring a combination of knowledge and networking experience which can help to connect to relevant projects such as iRECS, i-Consent, PREPARED, TechEthos, SHERPA, SIENNA, PANELFIT and ENERI. These connections will allow for mutual learning and reflections and synergies.

**This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon Europe program Global Health EDCTP3
Joint Undertaking Under Grant Agreement no. 101145644**